

Thermogravimetric Study of the Non-isothermal Decomposition of Ruthenium(II) and Platinum(IV) Complexes of 4-Amino-3-mercapto-6-methyl-1,2,4-triazin[4H]-5-one

ABRAHAM JOSEPH^a and B. NARAYANA^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, St. Pius X College, Rajapuram, Kasaragod-671 532

^bDepartment of Studies in Chemistry, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri-574 199

Manuscript received 17 March 1997, revised 28 July 1997, accepted 29 August 1997

This paper illustrates the thermal behavior of 4-amino-3-mercapto-6-methyl-1,2,4-triazin(4H)-5-one (AMMT) complexes of Ru^{II} and Pt^{IV}. The kinetic parameters are evaluated from the major decomposition part by a computed least-squares method using general (G), Coats-Redfern (CR), Freeman-Carroll (FC) and Horowitz-Metzger (HM) equations. The activation energy (*E*), Arrhenius parameter (*A*) and activation entropy are calculated. The values of kinetic parameters obtained by these different methods agree well. The thermal decomposition of these complexes follow first order kinetics. The negative values of entropy of the complexes indicate that the activated complex has more ordered structure than the reactants.

Theoretical :

The basic form of the equation used for analyzing non-isothermal data¹ is

$$\ln g(\alpha) = \ln \left[\frac{AE}{qR} \right] + \ln P(x)$$

where $P(x) = \int (e^{-x}/x^2) dx$, $x = E/RT$

A plot of $\ln g(\alpha)$ versus $1/T$ must be a straight-line for the correct order. In addition to this general approach, several equations are available for analyzing the non-isothermal TG curves. All these equations utilize this equation,

$$\frac{d\alpha}{f(\alpha)} = \frac{A}{q e^{-E/RT}} dT$$

in different approaches, namely, integral (Coats-Redfern), differential (Freeman-Carroll) and approximation (Horowitz-Metzger). In Coats-Redfern equation²,

$$\left[\frac{1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1-n}}{T^2(1-n)} \right] = \ln \frac{AR}{qE} \left[1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right] - \frac{E}{RT}$$

a plot of left-hand-side versus $1/T$ gives a straight-line for the correct order, *n*. In the differential method introduced by Freeman and Carroll³,

$$\frac{\Delta \ln(dw/dt)}{\Delta \ln W_r} = \frac{-E/R[\Delta(1/T)]}{\Delta \ln W_r} + n$$

a linear graph is expected for the plot of left-hand-side versus $1/T$ or $\Delta(1/T)/\ln W_r$, where *W* is the total loss in weight up to time *t*, $W_t = W_f - W$, where W_f is weight-loss at completion of the reaction and

$$\frac{dW}{dt} = \frac{dW}{dT} q$$

In Horowitz-Metzger equation⁴,

$$\ln \left[\frac{1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1-n}}{(1-n)} \right] = \ln \left[\frac{ART_s^2}{qE} \right] - \frac{E}{RT_s} + \frac{E\theta}{RT_s^2}$$

a linear graph is expected for the plot of left-hand-side versus θ for the correct order of the reaction. In all these equations except Horowitz-Metzger equation, the activation energy was calculated from the slope and frequency factor from the intercept value. In Horowitz-Metzger equation, *A* was calculated by

$$\frac{E}{RT_s^2} = \frac{A}{q e^{E/RT_s^2}}$$

The activation entropy was calculated by a general equation⁵,

$$S = R \ln \left[\frac{Ah}{kT_s} \right]$$

where *k* is the Boltzman constant, *h* the Plank constant, and T_s is the DTG peak temperature.

Results and Discussion

The TG, DTG and DTA traces are given in Figs. 1 and 2. Both the complexes decomposed in two stages. The major decompositions of these complexes were subjected to non-isothermal kinetic studies. The kinetic parameters such as *n*, *E*, *A* and *S* were evaluated. The phenomenological data of the thermal decomposition of Ru^{II} and Pt^{IV} are summarized in Table 1. The kinetic parameters calculated by a least-squares methods using different equations are listed in Table 2.

The Ru^{II} complex incurred a loss in weight when heated in the range 90–200°. This clearly indicates the presence of coordinated water molecules. The observed weight-loss at this temperature range is 7.89%. Then there is a sudden

Fig. 1. $\text{Ru}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{OS})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$.

Fig. 2. $\text{Pt}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{OS})_2(\text{Cl})_2$.

decrease in weight 12.0–64.0% in the temperature range 280–370° for Ru^{II} . This may be attributed to the oxidation of the organic matter and formation of the metal oxide. The cumulative weight change is maximum at this temperature. Further increase in temperature from 370 to 700° shows a slight change in weight and remains constant afterwards. The Pt^{IV} complex shows no change in weight up to 290°,

TABLE 1—PHENOMENOLOGICAL DATA OF THE THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF Ru^{II} AND Pt^{IV} COMPLEXES

Compd.	Decomp. temp. in TG(K)	Peak temp. (K)		Total weight-loss (%)		
		DTG	DTA	From TG	From pyrolysis	Theor.
$\text{Ru}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{OS})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	553–643	633	630	55.63	54.50	53.68
$\text{Pt}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{OS})_2(\text{Cl})_2$	563–713	654	650	58.10	59.32	60.93

TABLE 2—KINETIC PARAMETERS OBTAINED BY USING GENERAL APPROACH (G), COATS-REDFERN (CR), FREEMAN-CARROLL (FC) AND HOROWITZ-METZGER (HM) EQUATIONS

Compd.	Eqn.	E	A	S
		kJ mol^{-1}	s^{-1}	$\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
$\text{Ru}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{OS})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	G	33.44	1.58×10^3	-189.7
	CR	24.86	3.79×10^4	-163.3
	FC	28.64	3.87×10^2	-182.5
	HM	47.69	3.35×10^3	-202.6
$\text{Pt}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{OS})_2(\text{Cl})_2$	G	48.70	6.68×10^3	-178.2
	CR	32.48	5.68×10^3	-179.6
	FC	67.30	3.29×10^4	-165.0
	HM	49.40	2.45×10^3	-186.6

revealing the absence of coordinated water molecules. Then there is a gradual weight-loss of 5.8–46% in the temperature range 290–440°, which indicates the oxidation of all organic matter and formation of metal oxide. Further increase in temperature from 440 to 750° shows no significant weight-loss. The final decomposition products were analyzed to be oxides. The weight-loss data obtained from TG were compared with those obtained from independent pyrolysis experiments in which the samples were heated in a silica crucible above 500°. The weight-loss data from the TG and independent pyrolysis experiments agree well with the theoretical values (Table 1).

Usually the condition for gravimetric determination of metal ions are standardized by ascertaining the temperature of inception of decomposition of the complexes of the metal ion with the reagent which is used for the determination and also by finding out the correct temperature range for the resulting product to attain a constant weight. Here in case of the Pt^{IV} complex the decomposition begins well above 200° effective drying of the precipitate is possible, and as all of them retain the assigned formulae up to this temperature, the dry complexes can be weighed as such in gravimetric determinations.

Analysis of the data obtained by different equations indicates that the decomposition of these complexes follow first order kinetics. The activation entropy of the thermal decomposition of these complexes vary from -140 to -206 $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$. The negative values of activation entropy indicate that the activated complex has a more ordered structure than the reactants.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. 4-Amino-3-mercapto-6-methyl-1,2,4-triazin(4H)-5-one was synthesized by adding pyruvic acid to a boiling mixture of thiocarbonylhydrazide⁶ and water in 1 : 1.6 ratio. The yellow solid obtained on cooling the reaction mixture was crystallized from hot water⁷. The metal complexes were prepared by adding metal (Ru^{II} and Pt^{IV}) ion solutions to a boiling

NOTE

ethanolic solution of AMMT in a molar ratio of 1 : 2. The complexes were subjected to chemical analysis⁸.

The complexes were ground and sieved to 200–300 mesh. Thermograms of the samples were recorded in air using a Shimadzu DT-30 thermal analyzer : heating rate, 20°/min; atmosphere, static air; crucible, platinum. The numerical analysis of thermogravimetric data were performed using a computer program written in Microsoft BASIC.

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